

METHODS FOR THE DETERMINATION OF TRACE
ELEMENTS IN SOILS AND PLANTS. PART I.
DETERMINATION OF BORON AND
MANGANESE

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A new method has been described for the estimation of small amounts of boron (4 ppm) and Mn (80 ppm) in soils and plant samples.

It is now fairly well established that the presence of at least some of the minor elements in the soil is essential for normal plant growth. Such trace elements as boron, manganese, copper and zinc are necessary for the completion of the vegetative cycle of certain plants. It has, therefore, become necessary to develop and perfect the methods of analysis for the estimation of these elements in Indian soils and plant materials.

Methods in use. (a) *Spectrographic methods* :—Though accurate for the estimation of metallic trace elements up to 1 p. p. m. they are not widely popular on account of the elaborate equipment, expense and the training required in execution.

(b) *Colorimetric micro-chemical methods* :—Though at times tedious, particularly when estimating a number of trace elements in a series of samples, these are largely favoured on account of the ease of manipulation.

The present investigation was taken up in connection with the soil survey experiments conducted by this Institute and the methods for the estimation of boron, and manganese have been tested and standardised by examining the recoveries of varying amounts of added boron and manganese from six soil samples.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Double distilled water was used throughout the work.

(a) *Preparation of soil sample*.—Finely powered soil (2g.) was intimately mixed with 10g. of pure anhydrous sodium carbonate and fused in a platinum dish. After cooling it was placed in a 250 c.c. beaker containing 25 c.c. of distilled water. The contents were warmed after adding 10 c.c. of 4*N* sulphuric acid and covered with a clock glass. The addition of acid in 10 c.c. lots was continued until the melt had completely disintegrated and the residues had become colourless. The resulting solution and the washings were filtered into a 100 c.c. flask and made up to 100 c.c. after cooling. This formed the starting solution for the estimation of boron and manganese in the soil.

(b) *Examination of plant material for Boron and Manganese*.—To detect the differences in the mineral content of healthy and diseased plant materials the spectrographist solves the problem by incinerating the two samples under identical conditions and by comparing the two spectrograms, line by line, to detect any difference in the intensities of the two corresponding lines. They may later on be measured by microphotometry to get the absolute values for the two lines.

The micro-analyst ashes the samples under identical conditions, dissolves them in acid to a known volume and estimates the elements in question in aliquots. Work of this type has been carried out on healthy and various infected samples of tobacco leaf and the results are reproduced below.

Determination of Boron

The increasing use of boron as a fertiliser and the recognition of physiological disorders in plants due to boron deficiencies have resulted in the development of a number of methods for its estimation in soils and plant materials. Wilcox has applied the electrometric titration method for the purpose in the case of the soils and plants of the arid or semi-arid regions of the west where the boron concentration is fairly high. In the more humid regions with a lower concentration of boron, spectroscopic and the quinalizarin methods are in general use. Recently Neelakantam and Rangaswamy (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1943, 18A, 171) have reported a new colorimetric method for the estimation of boron in pure solutions depending on the yellow coloration obtained by boric acid with pentamethyl-querctin in presence of citric acid in anhydrous acetone medium. It is proposed to test this method in respect of soil and plant materials when a sufficient quantity of the reagent is available.

Of the several hydroxy-anthraquinones which have the property of changing colour when boron is added in concentrated sulphuric acid medium, quinalizarin has been found to be the most suitable, the colour changing from violet to blue with increasing concentration of boron. The colour is destroyed by oxidising agents and the sensitivity of the test depends upon the concentration of sulphuric acid, the final concentration of 93% being found most satisfactory. The method of Smith (*Analyst*, 1935, 60, 735) consists in pipetting 1 c.c. of the unknown or the standard solution into a graduated tube containing exactly 9 c.c. of 98.5% sulphuric acid. After thorough mixing and cooling, 0.5 c.c. of the quinalizarin solution (10 mg. in 100 c.c. of 93% sulphuric acid) is added and allowed to stand for 15 minutes and the unknowns are compared against standards prepared in exactly the same way.

Suitable colour standards have not yet been developed for this reaction. Hence a standard curve with varying amounts of boron (0.002 to 0.016 mg. per c.c.) compared with a blank, containing only distilled water as an index of concentration has been prepared employing the percentage of light transmission for the purpose. With this standard curve a secondary curve has been drawn for boron concentration varying from 0.0002 to 0.001 mg. per c.c.

It is necessary to use for fusion a large proportion of sodium carbonate for estimating the total boron content in the soil. It is advantageous to add sulphuric acid to the water for extracting the melt. Since the same solution was used to estimate manganese also, the melt was extracted with acid and addition of alcohol up to 70% by volume throws down most of the sodium sulphate formed. It is necessary to ignite the residue after the final evaporation to destroy any volatile organic matter present in the alcohol.

The technique of the colorimetric method using quinalizarin as perfected by Olson and DeTurke (*Soil Sci.*, 1940, 50, 257) has been adapted to Indian soils with a

few alterations in a Pulfrich photometer and all the reagents were prepared according to the instructions of Berger and Truog. The soil solution (25 c.c. containing 5g. of the soil) was pipetted into a conical flask, shaken with 150 c.c. of 95% ethyl alcohol and the supernatant liquid filtered into a 500 c.c. conical flask. After addition of 100 c.c. of distilled water to prevent subsequent precipitation and of potassium carbonate to make it just alkaline, the alcohol was distilled off to a small volume. The contents were then transferred to a platinum dish, evaporated to dryness and ignited. The residue was triturated with 5 c.c. of 0.36 *N*-sulphuric acid and transferred along with the washings of the dish to a 50 c.c. measuring flask and made up to the mark after cooling.

This solution (5 c.c.) was placed in a Nessler's tube, mixed with 45 c.c. of sulphuric acid (98.5%) and cooled. After adding 2.5 c.c. of 0.01% solution of quinalizarin the tube was lightly corked and allowed to stand at room temperature for at least 30 minutes. The intensity of the colour developed—(red-violet or blue-violet) was matched against a blank containing 5 c.c. of distilled water in place of the test solution. The percentage light transmissibility was measured in a Pulfrich photometer by placing the solutions in comparison vessels (30.11 cm. long)

The aperture of the photometer on the solution side was completely opened and the drum on the other side adjusted till an equal illumination was obtained through the light blue filter (L 3-37). The difference between the two drum readings gives the percentage of light cut down by the test solution when viewed through the light blue filter which is directly proportional to the concentration of boron. The amount of boron present in the reagents is subtracted from this value to get the total boron content of the soil. All the data in the tables have been approximated to the nearest integer.

TABLE I

Sample.	Serial No.	Conc. of boron in p p m.		
		in soil.	added.	recovered.
Surface soil (0-6") from Kalshakaka (Punjab)	599	28	50	48
			100	97
			150	146
Soil profile (0-1') from Gurdaspur (Punjab)	592	68	100	96
			200	198
			300	296
			320	316
Soil profile (0-1') from Lahore (Punjab) Virgin soil.	564	66	420	415
			520	516
Soil profile (0-1') from Kangra (Punjab)	585	86	200	197
			250	246
			300	297
Surface soil (0-9") from Burn's Garden (Karachi-Sind)	604	29	150	147
			225	221
			300	296
Soil profile (0-1') from Malir farm, Karachi (Sind)	608	32	225	223
			200	198
Blank for reagents.		0.2	275	271

Determination of Boron in healthy and Virus-infected samples of Tobacco.—Finely powdered plant material (2g.) was oven dried and ashed in a platinum dish. The ash was triturated with 5 c.c. of 3.6 *N*-sulphuric acid and filtered and washed into 100

c.c. measuring flask and made up to the volume after cooling. A 25 c.c. aliquot of this solution were evaporated nearly to dryness, redissolved in 20 to 25 c.c. of 0.36 N-sulphuric acid and made up to 50 c.c. 5 c.c. aliquots of this formed the test solutions. The details of further procedure were as described above in respect of soils with this difference that the experiments were conducted in duplicate as no recoveries were tested in their case. The results of analysis in duplicate of six samples of tobacco are given below.

TABLE II

Sample	Serial No.	Conc of boron in Expt. 1	P. P. M. Expt. 2.
I. P. H. 142-Healthy	795 of 1942	15	14
-do- Diseased	796 of 1941	20	20
Harrison's Special-Healthy	797 of ..	11	11
-do- Diseased	798 of ..	13	13
I. P. H. 142-Healthy	183 of 1942	11	11
-do- Diseased	184 of ..	11	11

Determination of Manganese in Soils.

Both micro and macro-methods have been in use for the estimation of manganese in soils, rocks and plants. The official gravimetric and volumetric methods recommended by the A. O. A. C. (1925 and 1930) are not, however, very popular and micro methods, for which elaborate technique has been developed, are in general use.

The colorimetric method of estimating manganese by oxidising the manganese salts to permanganate in strongly acid media with persulphates, periodates and peroxides of lead, bismuth etc., was adopted by a number of workers but with conflicting results depending on the particular oxidising agents employed. The pink colour developed in the reaction is matched against a standard of known manganese content.

Willard Greathouse (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 2366) were the first to establish the accuracy of the periodate method for the quantitative determination of manganese. This method has been successfully applied by different investigators, to water, animal and vegetable tissues, rocks and soils and salt solutions. A thorough spectrophotometric study of the method with special attention to the effect of the presence of other ions in the colour system has been made by Mehling (*Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1939, 11, 274) who established that, though the presence of a few of the 56 common ions interfere with the colour, the colour is stable for over two months and follows Beer's law. The production of colour is also independent of the presence of varying amounts of sulphuric acid, nitric and phosphoric acids or periodates.

Preparation of Mn Standard.—A stock solution of N/50-KMnO₄ is prepared by weighing the exact amount of the pure salt into a liter flask, dissolving and making up the solution to 1000 c.c. It is then filtered through glass wool into a stoppered

dry amber coloured bottle and kept in the dark at least for four days before standardising it. The exact volume of $N/50\text{-KMnO}_4$ (158.15 c.c.) required to make one liter of the desired concentration (0.1 mg. per c.c.) is taken in a litre flask, diluted with 100 c.c. of water before adding 20 c.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid. A solution of sodium bisulphite is slowly stirred into the mixture until the permanganate colour is just discharged. Any excess of sulphurous acid is oxidised by adding a few drops of concentrated nitric acid. After cooling the solution is made up to one litre.

Varying quantities of this solution were re-oxidised with phosphoric acid and sodium periodate and made up to 50 c.c. The colour of the resulting permanganate solution was compared with a blank carried out with distilled water and the reagents using light blue (L3-37) filter. The two solutions, standard and the blank, were placed in 10 c.c. comparison tubes with quartz faces and the maximum amount of light allowed to pass through the coloured standard. The drum on the side of the blank was adjusted till the intensity of light passing through the two tubes as viewed through the filter was the same. The reading on the drum was noted and repeated with the cells interchanged. The photometer difference was plotted against the concentration in mg. of KMnO_4 , in the total volume of the final solution (50 c.c.) for a series of standards and represented by a curve. Reagents required were concentrated sulphuric acid, concentrated nitric acid, phosphoric acid, —(d , 1.70) and sodium periodate (B. D. H. product).

(a) *Estimation of Manganese in soils.*—Soil extract (25 c.c.) after destroying the organic matter was taken in a silica crucible and heated on a water-bath with the addition of 5 c.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid to eliminate chlorides. At this stage 5 c.c. concentrated nitric acid followed by 1 c.c. of phosphoric acid were added and heated till all the nitrous fumes were driven off. To the mixture were added 20 c.c. of distilled water and 0.2 g. of sodium periodate and after careful boiling the resulting solution was kept undisturbed till the development of the pink colour was complete. After cooling the solution was made up to 50 c.c. Aliquots of this solution were taken in a 10 c.c. comparison cell and matched with a blank containing water and the reagents as described above in a Pulfrich photometer. Known amounts of manganese were added and the recoveries measured in the case of 6 soils. The results are expressed in parts per million in terms of potassium permanganate.

The above experiments show that the ions usually present in soil do not interfere with the colour formation.

The procedure adopted by Willard and Greathouse was followed in producing the colour system.

TABLE III.

Sample	Serial No.	Conc. of Mn as KMnO ₄ in p. p. m.		
		in soil	added	recovered
Surface soil (0-6') from Kalshakaka (Punjab)	599	2700	2500	2550
			5000	5045
			7500	7550
Soil profile (0-1') from Gurdaspur (Punjab)	592	3680	1000	1020
			1250	1275
			1500	1515
Soil profile (0-1') from Lahore (Punjab) Virgin soil	564	2450	3000	3040
			3240	3275
			3500	3545
Soil profile (0-1') from Kangra (Punjab)	585	4700	2000	2015
			2250	2275
			2500	2520
Surface soil (0-9") from Burns Garden, (Sind)	604	4800	1500	1510
			1750	1740
			2000	1985
Soil profile (0-1') from Malir farm, Karachi (Sind)	608	1360	1200	1220
			1700	1715
			2200	2240
Blank for reagents.		Nil		

Estimation of Manganese in healthy and virus infected samples of tobacco. The acid extract of the ash (25 c.c.) as prepared in the 6 cases for estimation of boron were taken in a silica crucible and the permanganate colour developed as described above. The experiments were conducted in duplicate for reproducibility and accuracy. The Mn content of six samples is given below.

TABLE IV.

Description. Sample	Serial No.	Conc. of Mn in p. p. m.	
		Expt. 1.	Expt. 2.
I. P. H. 142 Healthy	795 of 1941	139	137
Do. Diseased	796 of "	95	95
Harrison' special-Healthy	797 of "	100	100
Do. Diseased	798 of "	83	81
I. P. H. 142 Healthy	183 of 1942	70	72
Do. Diseased	184 of "	78	79

